

Theories of Poverty

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Abstract:- A lot of poverty writers explained that the conceptualization and dimension of poverty influence the ground rules of poverty policies and programs. This piece analyses the academic and empirical study on the causes of poverty and also how poverty can be controlled. The causes of poverty are many but these causes have been grouped under three main headings; individual influence, cultural influence and structural influence. Constructing a good knowledge on any of these opposing concepts shape the way in which poverty can be handled. Sustainable livelihood approach has been used in this article to share the concern that the economic well-being of the poorest of the poor ought to be understood from their perspective. The approach encourages a bottom-top methodology as it stresses that the poor should be at the core when developing any poverty reduction strategies for them. The source of data for this study is literature review (published books and other journal articles).

The paper may add more understanding into the ways in which poverty can be studied or handled. The paper strongly proposes that if poverty is caused by individual influence, the best way to deal with poverty should be to boost the emotional state of the poor through “self-help” strategies. This can be done by eliminating other forms of help given to the underprivileged in the form of family allowance. Family allowance encourages laziness. If poverty is caused by cultural influence, cultures should be replaced by a means that inspires creative work, assets, and collective responsibility. Lastly, if deficiency is caused by structural influence, there should be improvement in the schooling system. Government should create more jobs, and support the growth of micro, small, and medium businesses. This will bridge the inequality gap especially when a Sustainable livelihood approach is applied.

I. INTRODUCTION

Some poverty writers explained that the conceptualization and measurement of poverty influence the basic poverty strategies ^[1]. Sameti, Esfahani, & Haghighi, (2012) categorised the causes of poverty into three classes, individual, neighbourhood, and structural causes. Bradshaw (2006) on the other hand agreed with these authors that poverty can be assembled under three groups as mentioned by above authors but he also added other two causes of poverty, geographical disparities and cyclical interdependencies as the causes of poverty. Davis & Sanchez-Martinez (2015) argues that poverty can be categorized under Classical, Neoclassical, Keynesian and Marxist causes. Literature review suggests that much research has been done on the theories of poverty but there are no studies to assess theories of poverty and Sustainable Livelihood Approach. Against an examination of the theories of poverty, this article critically reviewed the

theoretic and experimental study on the causes of insufficiency and also how deficiency can be controlled. The causes of deficiency or insufficiency are many but they are going to be grouped under three main concepts in this article: (individual influence, cultural influence and structural influence). Sustainable Livelihood Approach (SLA) is used in the study to provide an understanding of best practices in addressing poverty. The source of information for this study is secondary data. Facts derived from unpublished or published works of others have been acknowledged in the text and a list of references are provided.

II. UNDERSTANDING POVERTY

Poverty is the ancient and the strongest ailment that brings an overwhelming disease in the world. Poverty affects development and political stability, disrupts nations, regions and individuals and remains a noticeable problem in the whole world ^[2] It has many structures, and varies from region to region ^[3].

In the early days, Gross National Product (GNP) was used to measure poverty. With this approach, poverty was measured based on the amount of income necessary to keep an individual alive ^[4]. According to this approach, the poverty dimension was based on the income level required to purchase the essential volume of lowest nutritional intake for sustaining life and calorie counts. Meaning poverty was the absence of appropriate wages or revenues in form of cash to buy or obtain the most elementary requirements such as food, shelter and clothing. According to the World Bank (2015) poverty line is 1.9 dollars per day. This means that if one is living on less than 1.9 dollars per day, one is underprivileged and will fall under the category of absolute poverty ^[5]. Absolute poverty can be defined as a state where a household lacks an income or financial means to get the basic goods and services necessary to live. E.G food, shelter, drinking water education etc. The above views do not consider the differences in regions, class and beliefs in societies in which households live ^[6]. For example, an individual can have an income which can buy elementary needs, but that individual can still possibly be underprivileged in comparison to one's region. This type of poverty is known as relative poverty ^[7]

According to Nsah (2013:10) relative Poverty can be described as the standard of living compared to economic standards of living within the same surroundings. With relative poverty, households are seen as underprivileged if they live below normal standards of living in a community ^[8]. This means that a family or a person can have some money but they will be considered poor because the income is still not enough to afford anything above the basics. In other words, “relative poverty” is the powerlessness to acquire what a person needs for a decent life ^[9]

It was believed that nations with high GNP rates would have a lesser volume of poverty than nations with low GNP but this was demonstrated wrong as some of the nations started to experience growths in GNP with rises in poverty at the same time. The fact is that increases in GNP were not evenly distributed among the citizens. The uneven distribution of the GNP increases the level of inequality. Those who receive little or nothing from the GNP continue to be poor because they are not benefiting from economic growth which could lead to social unrest^[10] The flaw of GNP statistics is that the sharing of the wealth across the citizens of a nation are not shown, all the same, the status of any nation is not only influenced by increase in GNP but by other factors including human capital, the legacy of the nation history, natural endowments, and the nature of governance^[11]

The above views provide compassionate understanding that being underprivileged can mean a lot more than merely not possessing some income. Amartya (1999) added that poverty also includes noiselessness and powerlessness of an individual in the community. According to Amartya, this type of poverty is when an individual lacks the ability to motivate a process or development programme/s that can have a positive impact on their personal life situation^[12]

Runguma (2014:28) suggested that in order to properly address a poverty situation, scholars and practitioners have to deal with the situation in a specific way. She suggested that the first phase should involve the definition of poverty. The second phase should be to measure the extent of the issue, which consists of the creation of techniques to measure it. Once the issue has been recognised, the last phase should be to determine its source. Answers have to be found to these questions: (what is poverty? What is the degree of poverty? What are the explanations of poverty?) Only then can one cross-examine what the cures to poverty are.^[13] Onyango (2011:6) on the other hand suggests that poverty definitions may possibly give wrong messages on how to tackle poverty. For him, a more relevant approach on how to study poverty should be well-defined primarily by the underprivileged who know their situation very well^[14] Borrowing from Runguma (2014) views, the next section of the study is going to discuss the sources of poverty.

A. Roots Of Deficiency

Constructing a full knowledge of the theories of poverty shape the way in which poverty can be handled as researchers argue that knowing the actual roots of poverty is significant as it informs people's perceptions on how to handle it. This section discusses the three opposing theories of poverty^[15]

B. Individual Influences

The individual influence attributes poverty to imperfections of the underprivileged themselves (Sameti, Esfahani & Haghighi, 2012). The theory places much importance on people's hard work and responsibility to acquire elementary needs. The concept illustrates that people should take charge of their life situations because they are in charge of their own lives^[16] Sameti et al (20:45)

argues that people are poor because they depend so much on social welfare contributions and as such they lack interest to battle poverty out. This theory is rooted in the United State where households are given huge openings to accomplish the vision of substantial prospect and achievement. Sameti et al. (2012:45) stress that capacity, assets and resilient work can result in greater achievement. Individuals at times are poverty stricken because they do not want to get involved in activities that will better their life situation. Here social problems such as unemployment can be a burden on the shoulders of individuals^[17]. From the above views one can say that the theory focuses on the explanation that individuals are responsible for their poverty situation. This means that those in poverty should be blamed for creating their own problems. Even in the bible, the poor are blamed for their situation. For example, Proverbs in the bible reveals that anyone who follows frivolity will highly be poor because poverty is associated with immoral activities, such as drunkenness, gluttony, gambling, and sloth (Proverbs. 10:4; 12:11, 20;13 23:21; 28:19). Schiller (2008) explains that harder work and better choices will get the poor out of poverty. However, Schwartz (2000) found little evidence to support this claim. He argues that children born into underprivileged families are much more likely to remain in poverty. Very few individuals born into poor families might escape poverty and many will die in poverty because hard work isn't the solution when the economic system works against the poor. Such circumstances fuel the cycle of poverty. Tamanji (2010) and Forgha (2006) believe that welfare programmes cause dependency on state administration as they argue that this concept gives a false impression that poverty is caused by individual influence. For example, as revealed in Nsah (2021) studies, one of the causes of poverty among the Bakas in the East Region in Cameroon is government's effort to expand and increase growth in the East Region which has forced the Baka to move out of the forest, which used to be their home, source of income and food. Causes of poverty in the Baka community here can be attributed to government role and not to Baka because those who are able and willing to carry out farming activities do not have available land for cultivation. Furthermore, there are also natural occurrences that cause poverty. For example, the Lake Nyos disasters in the North West region of Cameroon and the mountainous nature of the North West region of Cameroon will keep those who are willing and able to work in poverty(ibid) Other natural disasters that causes poverty include; floods, fires, earthquakes, tsunamis and cyclones^[18]

From the above views, it is certain that one can be poor because of natural occurrences even when one is willing and able to work. There are other causes of poverty such as joblessness, geographical locations, old age, and physical and mental disabilities that can cause poverty^[19] Even though it is challenging to disagree with the point that individual influence cannot limit one's position in society, it is also true that one's position in most societies function within boundaries defined by forces outside individual's control^[20] This theory, then, puts forward that for poverty to be reduced, the government and those who want to fight poverty should increase economic activities and encourage people to search for jobs, provide short-term employment to

those who are unemployed (Semati et al., 2012). This move can be accompanied by emphasising on “mutual support” plans, and the government should discourage or reduce family allowances given to the poor as assistance.

C. Structural Influences

The basic theory of neoliberal economic policies explained that income or earning disparities in the job market is the reason some people are poor (Hurst, 2004). According to Marx (1932) every goods has a market value and this market value is determined by the amount of labour invested in that goods. Davis & Moores (1945) argues that there are some jobs that require distinctive skills or knowledge to effectively carry out such a job and that such jobs deserve higher earnings because people undergo sacrifices to acquire such skills. Thus, work payment should be proportional to the cost of training. Hurst (2004) confirmed that the inequality in salaries is acceptable because skills or knowledge require training and during the training period income is lost because there is no labour. Meaning payment should be determined by the amount of time spent in learning a skill.

Figart & Power (2002) argues that in a competitive society there are some factors which tend to determine individual positions and earnings. E.g. Discrimination in the labour market increases inequality. Fischer (1992) explained that discrimination is socially constructed e.g. race, and gender. These factors either increase poverty or decrease it. Bonakele (2021) discusses that someone with exceptional expertise can still remain in poverty because of the communities in which they live. Alkire (2007) confirmed that because of discrimination certain groups of people will continue to find it difficult to gain employment even when they have the necessary skills because of structural and cultural influence in the job market (race and gender). Meaning education and training do not guarantee employment because economic structure influences individual level of poverty in any society irrespective of their strength such as hard work, skill, experience and willingness. Semati et al. (2012:8) further explained that in the domain of wage employment, individuals come to be underprivileged when they are under paid, and this practice of economic discrimination is the direct sign of deficiency. For example, joblessness takes place when an individual is discriminated against by the labour market. When someone loses a job, immediately he or she is deprived of access to regular income and their economic status is weakened towards poverty. Similarly, when an individual is deprived of material goods or services his economic status is also weakened towards poverty. A person's joblessness status can also damage one's social class ^[21] Amartya (1999) added that the distribution of scarce resources by the government is inefficient and ineffective and as such encourage deficiency This goes contrary to concepts and policy assumptions that dwell on the lack of “will and skill” obsessed by the poor themselves as being the major cause of their poverty ^[22]

D. Cultural Influence

Researchers argued that continual poverty in households will generate a cultural defiance, beliefs, sometimes generate some kind of behaviour that would tend to extend itself over time, even if the circumstances that first gave intensification to it changes. For example Hurst (2004), argues that with concept of cultural influence people do not have controllable emotions of marginality and vulnerability. People act like strangers in their own communities. He further added that the underprivileged every now and then are not willing to take part in useful activities simply because of the way they grow up in their community. Akerloff & Kranton (2002), added that learner's performance in school is influenced by their cultural identity. Lareau (2003) studies found that poor children may continue to be poorer over their generations simply because their relatives prefer cultural ways of doing things “normal growth”. This means that the underprivileged will continue to be poor and the affluent will continue to be rich because they have diverse patterns of beliefs and behavioural norms. Meaning the underprivileged come to be poor as they acquire strong emotional behaviours associated with poverty. From the above views, the underprivileged will continue to be poor because they do not have means to fight their poverty; for example, education and training are the keys to fight poverty but the underprivileged do not have resources to acquire the necessary skills in schools to enable them gain employment and reduce poverty.

Mandell & Schram (2003) condemned the culture of poverty for holding the underprivileged beliefs and their surroundings responsible for their lot. Rank (2004) indicates that human capital greatly disturbs an individual's earnings, and therefore absence of human assets can push people to fall in poverty. People with high knowledge or skills are more competitive in the labour market than people with low or no skill. From the above views, one can conclude that education and training are key to poverty reduction because people with high education face fewer problems being employed than those with less education. Moreover, they are less likely to be without a job, and the duration of their joblessness is usually shorter when compared to the situation of less educated individuals. The next section of the study focuses on poverty and livelihoods with more emphasis on Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA) as the best strategy for poverty reduction.

III. SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS APPROACH (SLA)

Sustainable Livelihood Approaches mean different things at different levels to different people ^[23] For example, for programme developers, it means pinpointing what combination of policies are more likely to have a greater supportive influence on economic growth, such as building good transportation networks and developing micro-credit facilities. Chambers and Conway (1992:4) perceive sustainable livelihoods as the connecting of three concepts; (1) increasing social sustainability, that is, vulnerability of the underprivileged ought to be minimized by decreasing external pressure and providing safety nets such as public allowances; (2) enhancing capability, that is, in facing

irregularity, people are flexible, speedy to adjust and exploit different opportunities. (3) Improving equity, the main concern ought to be given to the assets, capabilities and access of the poorest of the poor, including minorities and women.

Applying the SLA to poverty reduction will share the concern that the economic well-being of the poorest of the poor ought to be understood from their perspective and not from the perspective of an outsider. From the above view, poverty has numerous measurements and the circumstances of well-being for most household's changes over time. NSah (2023) assert that deficiency entails a holistic and participatory assessment of the range of livelihood activities that people draw upon, and of the strategies they employ. The available resources in fulfilling individual livelihood plans and overpowering their weakness to circumstances outside their control are very significant and, as such, poverty is not the focus, but rather building on their prosperity. Ashley & Carney (1999) argue that this approach is based on the principle that the underprivileged make premeditated choices according to their privileges and access to assets. For the purpose of this study, Krantz, (2001) definition of SLA is used. According to Krantz a livelihood is a set of activities necessary for daily life that are conducted over one's life span. E.g. Water, food, shelter, clothing. A livelihood is viable if it can handle and pull through pressures and still boost its abilities in the present and in the future while keeping its natural resource base. These explanations emphasise that a sustainable livelihood must offer substantial work that will satisfy the social, economic, cultural and spiritual needs of a society both present and in the future, but still safeguard cultural and natural diversity. This revealed that a decent description of sustainable livelihoods ought to go further than elementary requirements of life such as water, food, and shelter but include good quality of life that is rooted in prosperous societies ^[24]

The sustainable livelihood approach is used in this study to illustrate how individuals can prepare for and respond to changes in their environment. Furthermore, the approach is an important analytical tool that illustrates how external factors consisting of macro-economic factors, history and politics generally influence the poor in the society. Nyathi (2012:45) indicates that numerous approaches have been unsuccessful to reduce poverty and stresses that anyone who wants to reduce poverty can apply this approach as it focuses on normal resources to improve living conditions. Cárdenas Oleas (2015) argues that although some individuals or organisations can not officially apply this approach for poverty alleviation plans, however, the approach is a valuable instrument that can be used to evaluate their work and how it assists peoples' means of support. The approach stresses the involvement of the poor in the identification and implementation of activities. Roodt (2001:470) indicates that some of the reasons it is difficult to reduce poverty is that most developers' activities are based on top-down project plans instead of bottom-up approaches to deliver change to the community. The top-down approaches most often do not really think through feasibility and thus after much has been spent in terms of

resources and time, there is little or nothing to show for it ^[1] The advantage of this method is that it positions the underprivileged and their conditions firmly at the centre of the investigation and equally offers a general view of the lives of the poor that fits well with multi-level conceptualization of poverty.

A. The core principles underpinning SLA are ^[25]

- **People centred:** Krantz (2001) clarifies that a viable poverty alleviation can be accomplished if outside assistance centres on what is important to people, recognises the changes between individuals groups, and build on their capacity in a way that is well-suited to their existing living approaches or community setting, and capability to adjust. This means that for any project or activity to yield good fruit in the community, the underprivileged who know their poverty situation more than anyone should be at the centre of that project. However, the state role is still necessary to support and stimulate people's needs, but change in the conception of people-centred development is the best approach. Roodt (2001) argues that growth does not start with material belongings; it begins with individuals and their training, good system of government, and discipline. From this view, unless life expectancy of the people is appropriately considered and managed accordingly, the developmental process will be a useless effort because economic growth alone cannot represent real development [26]. NSah (2023) in line with Matiku, Zuwarimwe & Tshipala, (2021), advises that "development processes should carry the aspirations and define the needs of the people for allocating, mobilizing, and managing resources which can strengthen the communities". According to this author, growth is not like stuff which can be rented from outside. To him, genuine growth cannot be attained with foreign aid or assistance alone. People must be involved in carrying out developmental activities that require authentic participation if they want to benefit from the developmental process.
- **Being responsive and participatory:** Every individual has a strong point. Meaning that any intervention to deal with poverty should be built on people straight or on their strong point (Roodt 2001). This means that any project that has to deal with poverty, the beneficiaries of the project should be involved in the project from the beginning to end. The goals of participation are accomplished when everyone has a saying in decision making. Participation starts from situation assessment, planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation and ends by celebrating the success. It is not a once-off plan but a learning practice for all the participants. Participation encourages empowerment. Empowerment here implies the process through which community members gain skills, knowledge, understanding and control on how to manage economic, social, cultural and political powers in order to develop and improve their livelihood. The advantages of participation in community development is that community members will take ownership of their own development and self-reliance, and utilise their power to improve their living conditions [27] However some researcher like Ashley & Carney (1999) argues that participation sometimes cause delay in

development project because people have different views on what need to be done. This is time-consuming which makes the delivery process longer than when decisions are made by few.

- **Working with partners:** The method emphasizes the significance of forming partnerships. Partnerships can be developed with underprivileged and their organisations, e.g. partnerships can be formed with NGOs and their beneficiaries. Partnerships should be transparent arrangements, built upon shared goals [28]
- Being dynamic; Means of support and the elements influencing them are continuously changing. The method should try to support constructive ways of change and create longer-term assurances.
- **Disaggregate:** It is dynamic to apprehend how resources, voices and livelihood approaches vary among affluent groups and underprivileged groups as well as between males and females in these groups.

With this approach it is easy to possibly evaluate different impacts on livelihood strategies of individuals or households. The activities that will have an impact on livelihoods include, providing work or job opportunity,

income and food security, training and skills development, healthcare, safety and empowerment. With this approach, the poor themselves should be the key actors in detecting and addressing livelihood main concerns as the approach necessitates an understanding of what people need and want most[29]

B. SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FRAMEWORK

This is a framework that assists in studying the means of support of the underprivileged. The aim of the framework is to show how the poor can detect the issues that shake their means of support, comparative status and the manner in which they interrelate. The framework views the underprivileged as those functioning in an environment of vulnerability, however, there are some basic resources around them that they can use to reduce their vulnerability. The environment also impacts the means of support schemes that are exposed to the underprivileged in search of valuable means of support that meet their own livelihood intentions. It is adopted from the sustainable livelihood framework used by DFID in the late 1999's

[1] Roodt, 2001

Fig. 1: Sustainable livelihoods framework

The above conceptual framework emphasizes a people centred approach. The framework helps in understanding how underprivileged can pull on capabilities and possessions to improve living plans made up of a series of undertakings. The framework outlines diverse forms of possessions and privileges which the underprivileged have control over. The framework studies the diverse features in small and broader settings that affect individual living

sanctuaries and examines the relationship amongst the actors, organizations and processes in the wider world. The framework is built around five important groups of means of support system, namely, livelihood strategies, livelihood assets, vulnerability context, transforming and processes structure, and livelihood outcome.

According to Krantz (2001) sustainable livelihood framework was developed as an alternative way of conceptualising deficiency, as well as its framework. The approach is more about the necessary aspects of life i.e. the ability of the underprivileged to support their lives and their relatives for always. Sustainable living or livelihood structures will be elaborated in greater details below as follows:

- **Vulnerability Context:** DFID (1999) explained that people's livelihoods are fundamentally affected by critical inclinations (population, resource, economic, and governance) as well as shocks that distress individuals' means of support. Shock here consists of clashes, health complications, and natural disasters, such as epidemic, animal diseases, floods, and earthquakes. Seasonality consists of prices and employment opportunities over which they have limited or no control. To deal with vulnerability context entails identifying trends, shocks and aspects of seasonality that are of particular importance to means of support.
- **Livelihood Assets:** Individuals need different means of support to attain optimistic livelihood outcomes. Therefore, absence or lack of resources in terms of income, and other opportunities that may better the living condition is a cause of insufficiency. According to Krantz (2001), Livelihood Assets comprises natural capital. These are natural means that can be used by the underprivileged to accomplish their living objectives, e.g. wildlife, biodiversity and environmental services. Physical capital are inputs required at every stage of production. E.g. raw material, real estate, building. In order word, physical capital are production tools. Financial capital comprises financial possessions such as money, bank notes, pension and regular remittances that can be used by the needy to attain a better living. Human capital comprises skills, strength, understanding, information and ability that can make it possible for the needy to apprehend different living strategies and achieve living goals. Social capital comprises, social systems, association, connection, support, entrance to wider institutions or organisation through which individual gain assistance to build their livelihood objectives [30]
- **Transforming Structures and Processes:** These are institutions and policies that influence the underprivileged lives. Transforming Structures consist of hardware that involves government and non-governmental segments at all stages. Policy, law, culture, institutions and power relations are all examples of processes. All these elements are more like software, they can transform susceptibility setting and possessions which the underprivileged have control (DFID, 1999)
- **Livelihood Strategies:** These are those activities that the underprivileged undertake to achieve their living goals. In other words, these are activities which are employed to generate the means of family survival [31] Matiku et al (2021) classifies (income from crops and livestock) as normal resource based and (rural employment, rural service, property rentals, retirement pensions, urban and international remittances) non-natural resource based [32]

- **Livelihood Outcome:** Sustainable Livelihood framework DFID (1999) refers to what people may obtain tomorrow through livelihood activities. Matiku, et al (2021) recognizes two classes of outcomes. The first class is concerned with an individual's working hours, advancement of contentment and proficiencies. The next class is based on adaptability, flexibility, and sustainable use of normal means [33] In Krantz (2001), livelihood outcomes is more about how to increase income, deal with vulnerability, enhanced foodstuff safety, and best ways to exploit raw material base. Meaning that in order to reduce poverty, those who are concerned need to introduce the use of local base raw material. This strategy will offer the locals a long-term dependable source of income. [34]

C. Strengths Of The Sustainable Livelihood Approach

The approach is important in this study because it encourages a bottom-top approach. The approach stresses that the poor should be at the core when developing poverty reduction strategies. The approach recognises that the poor also have strengths including physical and natural resources [35] Results from contemporary participatory poverty assessments demonstrate that deficiency is not just the lack of basic but renunciation of luxury life .

Furthermore, the Approach has assisted in the understanding of the principal reasons that increases or decreases the level of poverty in communities as it's easy to assess the available resources in the communities [37]. In addition, the method creates a possibility to understand how the poor can gain strength and make decisions that can positively improve their living standard. In addition, it permits a more vibrant perspective on livelihoods, since individual powers are not constant, they can change at times either because of their surroundings or because of external environment [38]. The approach is used in this study because if it is applied effectively, it can contribute to veritable poverty reduction.

D. LIMITATIONS OF THE SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS APPROACH

Despite all the great benefits that the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach provides for poverty reduction, the approach has some criticism. Helmore & Singh (2001) established the following weaknesses in the application of the approach.

The first criticism about this approach is that it does not deal with the problem of how to recognise those who are really in need of assistance and the actual underlying core of the SLA is poverty reduction. As seen above, being underprivileged can mean a lot more than simply not having any income or that poverty is well-defined as absence of enough income in cash or exchange items for obtaining the most elementary requirements like education, water, food, shelter, and clothing. There is more to poverty than just lack of basic necessities. In a community people are faced with diverse needs since poverty is not homogeneously spread within a community as every single community has people who are better off than others. In addition, the approach does not offer a clear scheme to handle individual positioning, their knowledge and sensitive cares. Similarly,

the way assets and other living prospects are spread locally and are time and again determined by natural structures of social authority and power within the people themselves. Therefore poverty cannot simply be reduced only to economic deprivation

Another criticism is that gender is one of the characteristics of communal relationships. There is high discrimination and social supremacy between males and females relationships. The approach has not helped to show how gender can be addressed in principle, for example, the genuine perceptions, interests, and needs of women in relation to specific livelihood issues in practice is difficult to handle using this approach.

Finally, the approach cannot be used continuously because if the approach is used every day it might be beyond the actual genuineness of numerous local development managers, with the danger that this method remains as a good deed to funders^[39]. Despite these criticisms, the approach offers a more appropriate technique to evaluate poverty and provides a framework through which poverty can be reduced.

IV. CONCLUSION

Drawing from above illustration one can suggest that underprivileged are those operating within harsh external surroundings and they are subjected to different pressures and limitations. Below are some of the suggestions to deal with the causes of poverty as discussed above. To begin with, if poverty is caused by individual influence, the best solution will be to encourage the needy to search for jobs, and this can be done through counselling. Another strategy can be through reduction of assistance given to the underprivileged in the form of family allowance but Semati et al. (2012) suggested that there should be an increase in assistance given to the disabled and elderly to fight poverty. The study further suggests that if poverty is caused by cultural influence, communities or individuals should be encouraged to educate the elderly who are custodian of their culture to know the negative impact of these cultures so that they can replace the values with beliefs that inspire creative work, investment, and communal responsibility.

Thirdly, if poverty is caused by structural influence, the solution will be to change that particular system. If households are poor because they have inadequate human capital or lack technical expertise, the government should improve schooling for the poor by giving scholarships, since education and training are the keys to fight poverty and the underprivileged do not have resources to acquire these necessary skills to enable them gain employment. Government should create more jobs, and support the development of micro, small, and medium businesses. This will bridge the inequality gap. Since the sources of poverty are very much multifaceted, the study strongly believed that poverty can be well-defined primarily by the underprivileged who know their situation very well and the best approach to tackle poverty is SLA because poverty is diverse and means different things

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abia, W., Nchanji, E., Markjovert, A, Eucharia A., Abia, E. 2016. Valorisation of NGOs' existence in Cameroon: Option for a more engaged civil society (vnec-oecs). International Journal of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Essays, vol.1 no.1, pp.1-17. European Centre for Research Training and Development, UK.
- [2.] Akerloff, G., & Kranton.R. 2002. Identity and schooling: Some lessons for the economics of education. Journal of Economic Literature 40:1167-2101.
- [3.] Alkire, S. 2007. Choosing dimensions: The capability approach and multidimensional poverty. CPRC Working Paper, 88, 1-25.
- [4.] Amartya Sen, Development as Freedom, (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1999) Ashley, C. & Carney, D. 1999. Sustainable livelihoods: Lessons from early experience. Nottingham: Russell Press Ltd.
- [5.] Bonakele, P. 2021. Understanding Sustainable Livelihood Strategies Of Female-Headed Households: The case of Renosterberg municipality, pixleyka seme district, Northern Cape. Faculty Of Economic and Management Science. University of the Free State
- [6.] Bourgois, P. 1997. In Search of Respect: Selling Crack in El Barrio Cambridge: University Press.
- [7.] Bradshaw, T.K. (2006) Theories of Poverty and Anti-Poverty Programs in Community Development. Rural Poverty Research Centre (RPRC) Working Series No.06-05 Oregon State University and University of Missouri
- [8.] Cárdenas, S. E. 2015. Case study: a sustainable livelihoods analysis of a non-governmental organization working with quinoa producers in the province of Chimborazo, Ecuador. Graduate Theses and Dissertations.Paper 14336.
- [9.] Carter, P. 2005. Keeping' it real: School success beyond black and white. New York: Oxford University Press Chambers, R. & Conway, G. R. 1992. Sustainable rural livelihoods: Practical concepts for the 21st Century, Discussion paper 296. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies.
- [10.] Davis, K. & Moore, W. (1945). Some principle of stratification. American Sociological Review, 10 (2), 242-249.
- [11.] Davis, E & Sanchez-Martinez, M, . 2015. Economic theories of poverty. Available at www.jrf.org.uk
- [12.] Department for International Development (DFID). 1999. Sustainable livelihoods guidance sheets. Available: <http://www.livelihoodscentre.org/documents/20720/100145/Sustainable+livelihoods+guidance+sheets/8f35b59f-8207-43fc-8b99-df75d3000e86>.
- [13.] Eddins, E. 2013. A sustainable livelihoods approach to volunteer tourism: the roles of the host community and an alternative break program in Achiote, Panama. Colorado State University, Fort Collins, Colorado.

- [14.] Ekane, D. 2010. The Context of an Urban Social problem in Cameroon: Case study of youth unemployment. University of Stockholm, Department of social work (Master's Thesis).
- [15.] Figart, M., & Power, M. (2002). Living wages, equal wage: Gender and labor market policies in the United States: New York, NY: Routledge
- [16.] Fisher, G. (1992). The development of the Orshansky's poverty thresholds and their subsequent history as the official poverty measure. Available www.census.gov/hhes/www/povmeas/papers/orshansky.html.
<http://www.ers.usda.gov/publications/rdr100/rdr100.pdf>
- [17.] Forgha, N. 2006. Econometric Model of Poverty in Cameroon: International Review of Business Research Papers, 2(2): 30-46.
- [18.] Graaf, J. 2003. Poverty and development. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [19.] Harding, D. 2010. Living the drama: Community, conflict, and culture among inner-city boys Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- [20.] Helmore, K., & Singh, N. 2001. Sustainable livelihoods: Building on the wealth of the poor. Bloomfield, CT: Kumarian Press, Inc.
- [21.] Hurst, C. (2004). Social inequality: Forms, causes and consequences. New York, NY: Person Education Inc.
- [22.] Krantz, L. 2001. The Sustainable Livelihood Approach to Poverty Reduction. An Introduction. Executive Summary. pp. 6-21. Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency. Division for Policy and Socio Economic Analysis. Available file:///C:/Users/owner/Downloads/Sustainablelivelihoods.pdf.
- [23.] Laderchi, C., Saith, R. & Stewart, F. (2003). Does it matter that we do not agree on the definition of poverty: A comparison of four approaches. Oxford Development Studies, 31 (3), 233-274.
- [24.] Lareau, A. 2003. Unequal childhoods: Class, race, and family life. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- [25.] Mah, V.A. 2016. Sustainability of community-managed projects in the North West Region of Cameroon. Cardiff Metropolitan University (PhD thesis).
- [26.] Marx, K. 1932. The Economic and philosophical of manuscripts. Available <http://www.wehavephotoshop.com/PHILOSOPHY%20NOW/PHILOSOPHY/Marx/Marx,,Karl.-.Economical.And.Philosophical.Manuscripts.pdf>.
- [27.] Matiku, Zuwarimwe, & Tshipala, 2021. Sustainable tourism planning and management for sustainable livelihoods. Development Southern Africa, 2021, Volume 38, Number 4, Page 524 Available. https://citations.springernature.com/item?doi=10.1007/978-981-10-0983-9_5
- [28.] Nsah E.S. 2023 Gaps between NGOS Polices and their Implementation in The North West Region, Cameroon, International Journal of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and Essays, Vol.7, No 1, pp. 1-19
- [29.] Nsah, E. 2021. Non-governmental Organisations and poverty reduction in the North West and East regions of Cameroon. University of Cape Town. PHD thesis
- [30.] Nsah, E. 2013. Food garden and poverty reduction in Grabouw, South Africa. University of the Western Cape, Department of Development Studies (Master's thesis).
- [31.] Nyathi, D. 2012. An evaluation of poverty alleviation strategies implemented by NGOs in Zimbabwe. University of Fort Hare. Department of Development Studies (Master's thesis).
- [32.] Onyango, P. 2011. Poverty Alleviation in Small-Scale Fisheries: Governance Challenges in Lake Victoria Fishing Communities, Tanzani. University of Tromsø Ouane, Available http://www.unesco.org/education/uie/publications/uie_stud41.shtml
- [33.] Pettinger, T. 2017. Definition of absolute and relative poverty. Available: <https://www.economicshelp.org/blog/glossary/definition-of-absolute-and-relative-poverty/>
- [34.] Rank, M. (2001). The effect of poverty on America's families: Assessing our research knowledge. Journal of Family Issues, 22 (7), 882-903
- [35.] Rank, M. 2004. One nation underprivileged: Why American poverty affects us all. New York, NY: Oxford Press.
- [36.] Roodt, M. 2001. Participation, civil society and development. In Coetze, J. K. et al. (Eds.). Development: Theory, policy and practical. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 469-481.
- [37.] Runguma, S. 2014. The political economy of poverty reduction in Kenya. University of Witwatersrand Johannesburg, Faculty of humanities. (PhD Thesis).
- [38.] Sameti, M., Esfahani, R., Haghighi, H. 2012. Theories of Poverty: A Comparative Analysis. Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review 33(835):1-16
- [39.] Schiller, R.B. 2008. The economics of poverty and discrimination. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [40.] Schwartz, J. 2000. Fighting poverty with virtue. Bloomington: Indiana University.
- [41.] Tamanji, A. 2011. Three Instances of Western Colonial Governments and Christian Missions in Cameroon Education. The Faculty of Graduate School in Candidacy: Loyola University Chicago (PhD thesis).
- [42.] Tao, T.C.H. & Wall, G. 2008. Tourism as a sustainable livelihood strategy. Tourism Management, 30: 90-98.
- [43.] Thomas, C. 2015. Poverty and inequality. In Stewart, P. & Zaيمان, J. (eds). Cape Town: Juta Sociology a Concise South African Introduction,
- [44.] The World Bank. 2015. "The international poverty line has just been raised to \$1.90 a day, but global poverty is basically unchanged. How is that even possible?" <https://blogs.worldbank.org/developmenttalk/internati>

- onal-poverty-line-has-just-been-raised-190-day-
global-poverty-basically-unchanged-how-even
- [45.] Laderchi, Saith & Stewart, 2003
 - [46.] The World Bank, 2015
 - [47.] Laderchi, Saith & Stewart, 2003
 - [48.] Graaff, 2003
 - [49.] Pettinger, 2017; Thomas, 2015
 - [50.] Graaf, 2003
 - [51.] Amartya, 1999
 - [52.] Nsah, 2013:10
 - [53.] Amartya, 1999
 - [54.] Graaff, 2003
 - [55.] Lardechi et al, 2003
 - [56.] Amartya, 1999
 - [57.] Runguma, 2014
 - [58.] Onyango, 2011.
 - [59.] Rank, 2001
 - [60.] (Ekane, 2010).
 - [61.] Sameti et al. (2012:45)
 - [62.] (Mah, 2016).
 - [63.] (Nsah, 2021).
 - [64.] (Nsah, 2021).
 - [65.] (Graaff, 2003).
 - [66.] (Semati et al., 2012).j
 - [67.] (Krantz, 2001).
 - [68.] (Department for International Development (DFID), 1999).
 - [69.] (Krantz, 2001);
 - [70.] (Matiku, Zuwarimwe & Tshipala, 2021)
 - [71.] (Matiku et al, 2021).
 - [72.] (Roodt, 2001).
 - [73.] (Krantz, 2001).
 - [74.] (Krantz, 2001).
 - [75.] (Krantz, 2001).
 - [76.] (Matiku et al, 2021).
 - [77.] Matiku et al, 2021).
 - [78.] (Matiku et al, 2021).
 - [79.] (Roodt, 2001).
 - [80.] (Nsah, 2013).
 - [81.] (Tao & Wall, 2008
 - [82.] (Krantz, 2001).
 - [83.] Eddins, 2013